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Research article

A life cycle sustainability assessment of organic and conventional pork supply chains in Sweden

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ABSTRACT

Most existing life cycle assessment studies that have compared the sustainability of organic and conventional pork supply chains are environmental assessments. The economic and social sustainability dimensions of pork supply chains are currently under-researched. The study reported here was designed to assess the environmental, economic and social sustainability of conventional and organic pork in Sweden. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment was undertaken using 20 indicators expressed per unit product (1000 kg pork fork weight) and per unit area (1000 ha of farmland) for the four main subsystems in pork supply chains: (1) farm and feed production, (2) slaughter, (3) wholesaling and retailing, and (4) consumption. The organic pork supply chain out-performed the conventional chain in 11 of the 20 indicators expressed per unit product and 18 of the 20 indicators expressed per unit area. It was therefore the more sustainable of the two chains in nearly all the indicators expressed per unit area. However, the organic supply chain was less sustainable in some of the indicators expressed per unit product because more feed per kg of pork was required in organic pork production. Pig welfare improvement leads to higher production costs and environmental impacts. Assessment of all three sustainability dimensions – environmental, economic and social – helps to identify trade-offs between these three pillars of sustainability. However, the selection of indicators influences results, and obtaining environmental, economic and social data simultaneously is challenging.

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1. Introduction

Pork is the most produced terrestrial meat product in the world today with production having quadrupled over the last 50 years (FAO 2021). In 2021, global pork production is expected to increase by 2% to 103.8 million tonnes of pork with China being the largest producer with 40% of the world's production and at the same time being the largest consumer (USDA 2021). Sweden is one of the leading countries in terms of socially sustainable pork production (Zira et al. 2020), with low use of antibiotics (SVA 2020) and high animal welfare supported by law (SFS 1988). Aiming for a sustainable pork production, there is room for improvement in Sweden as well as other countries, but multidisciplinary analyses of environmental, economic and social sustainability issues on

pork supply chains are generally lacking (Gunnarsson et al. 2020; Bonneau et al. 2014).

The European Green Deal sets out strategies to address these sustainability issues. In it, reductions in the use of pesticides, antibiotics and fertilizers are proposed, as well as other strategies including reduced food waste, increased focus on innovation and improved provision of information to society (e.g. through labelling) (EP 2020). The food industry also engages in improving sustainability of food, for example by the use of private certification schemes and providing its own environmental and social information on production practices. For example, there is certification of organic products for which both EU regulations exists (EC 2007) and private certification schemes which augment the EU regulations (e.g. KRAV in Sweden). These allow citizens to make more informed purchasing decisions when buying food products (Kanis et al. 2003).

Life cycle assessment (LCA) has been used in the past to assess the sustainability impacts of various livestock products, including pork. Much of the focus has been on assessing the environmental

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Nomenclature

APOS	at point of substitution
B_0	methane generation potential
BDP	biodiversity damage potential
$CD_{W/R}$	costs of distribution for wholesaler and retailer (excluding salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes)
CMA_p	costs of product manufacturing at the farm (excluding wages, salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, taxes)
CO_S	costs of operating the slaughterhouse (excluding salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes)
CPA_S	costs of packaging for slaughterhouse
$CRE_{W/R}$	costs of retail for the wholesaler and retailer (excluding salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes)
CTR_p	costs of transport for the farmer
CTR_S	costs of transport for the slaughterhouse
$CTR_{W/R}$	costs of transport for the wholesaler and retailer
FDP	fossil depletion
FEP	freshwater eutrophication potential
FET	freshwater ecotoxicity
GWP100	global warming potential over 100 years
HTP	human toxicity potential
IND_{conv}	environmental, economic or social indicator values for the conventional supply chain
IND_{org}	environmental, economic or social indicator values for the organic supply chain
ISO	international standard organization
LCC	life cycle costs
LCC_p	life cycle costs of the farmer
LCC_S	life cycle costs of the slaughterhouse
$LCC_{W/R}$	life cycle costs of the wholesaler and retailer
LCSA	life cycle sustainability assessment
MCF	methane conversion factor
MEP	marine eutrophication potential
MET	marine ecotoxicity
PET	polyethylene terephthalate
RSP	relative sustainability points
SCL100	soil carbon loss over 100 years
SEK	swedish krona (around 0.1 euro)
SR	social risk
SRT	social risk time
T	activity variable
TAP100	terrestrial acidification potential over 100 years
TET	terrestrial ecotoxicity
VA	value added
VS	volatile solids

impacts in environmental LCA (E-LCA). More studies with a holistic approach, like the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), which incorporates all three sustainability dimensions, are required for pork supply chains to identify opportunities for improvement and enable a shift towards more sustainable business models.

Therefore, the present study was designed to perform an LCSA for two contrasting pork supply chains in Sweden, one conventional and one organic, in order to identify the elements, or prerequisites, of more sustainable pork supply chains. The study's results are important in determining appropriate management strategies in the quest for fair, healthy and environment-friendly pork production under the European Green Deal (EP 2020).

2. Literature review

2.1. Environmental, social and economic concerns of pork production

Pig production systems drive deforestation in South America because they rely on soybean feed (approximately 20% of soybean exports from Brazil to the EU are linked with deforestation (Rajão et al. 2020)). They contribute to extensive land use in the production of feed crops (zu Ermgassen et al. 2016), and to water and soil pollution through their dependence on fertilizers and pesticides in crop production. Fertilizer use, together with the manure production and management, fossil fuel use for crop production, and the transportation of products from production sites to markets, all contribute to greenhouse gas emissions (Gerber et al. 2013). In terms of social sustainability, Zira et al. (2020) found that pork supply chains had issues including accidents at the slaughterhouse, unsatisfactory social benefits for workers at soybean farms, gender inequality for soybean workers in Brazil, health risks to workers stemming from pesticide use in soybean production, musculoskeletal disorders in farmers and workers at pig farms, and limited opportunities for pigs to express their natural behavior as a result of intensification. On the economic front, the sustainability issues that pork supply chains face include low incomes for farmers (Zira et al. 2020; van Wagenberg et al. 2017).

Several LCA studies on European pork supply chains have been published to date. Most are E-LCA and have system boundaries up to either the farm gate or slaughter gate, i.e. they are limited to the environmental impacts of pork production before the pork gets to the retailers (e.g. Monteiro et al. 2019; Noya et al. 2017; Sonesson et al. 2016). However, a few have included the retail and consumption stages (Bonou et al. 2020; Moberg et al. 2019; Head et al. 2014). To date, although sustainable business models require not only on environmental sustainability but also economic and social sustainability (Gunnarsson et al. 2020; Lin et al. 2020), only a few studies have examined the economic (Lotti and Bonazzi 2014) and social (Zira et al. 2020) sustainability of pork production.

2.2. Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Assessment (ISO 14044) is a standardized method of assessing impacts of a product/service (ISO 2006). Life Cycle Assessment was conceived in the 1960s in response to concerns about environmental degradation and use of resources (Bjørn et al. 2018). The first LCA in the 1960s focused on packaging of food (Agrifootprint 2020) and later in the 1970s much focus was on energy (Andersson et al. 1994). The first LCA on agricultural products was on tomatoes in 1990 (Agrifootprint 2020) and LCA broadened to include animal products in the early 1990s in Europe (Andersson et al. 1994). Life cycle costing was first performed in the 1960s by the United States Department of Defense (Guinée et al. 2011). There is no standardization of life cycle costing methods and many applications are on durable products such as buildings (Settanni et al. 2010). Very few life cycle costing studies on food products have been performed (Konstantas et al. 2019). S-LCA is relatively new, as LCA experts formed the Life cycle initiative in 2002 to broaden LCA to include the social dimension and the guidelines for S-LCA were published in 2009 (Huertas-Valdivia et al. 2020). Using the guidelines, the first S-LCA on animal products was on milk (Chen and Holden 2017).

In LCA, impacts are commonly assessed per kg of product produced. A mass-based functional unit is useful for calculating the total emissions from total human food consumption. However, Salou et al. 2017 recommend the use of both a mass-based unit and assessing impacts per area, e.g. per hectare of land used, when

performing LCA on agricultural systems. The use of mass-based comparisons alone miss important aspects related to intensification of production, e.g. that point pollution might increase when the use of inputs increase per hectare, hence risking non-optimal decision making (Muller and Schader 2017). These two units of comparisons, so called 'functional units' in LCA vocabulary, also reflects different perspectives of sustainability in food systems. The traditional mass-based unit relates to the dominant 'efficiency' perspective that focuses on increasing productivity in order to decrease emissions per unit product, while demand is considered largely given by current trends (Garnett 2014). The efficiency perspective does not deal with potential overconsumption of livestock products with a low impact per kg resulting in higher impact in absolute terms. In the contrasting 'sufficiency' perspective, focus is put on the possibility and need to manage demand to reduce overall emissions and resource use (Garnett 2014). The sufficiency perspective hence views the available agricultural land as the boundary condition rather than the need to produce a certain exogenously determined amount of meat (van Zanten et al. 2018). For this perspective, a per area functional unit is also relevant as here the focus is on the efficient use of land (Röös et al. 2021).

2.3. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

Conceptually, LCSA has three components: environmental (E-LCA), economic (Life Cycle Costing) and social (Social Life Cycle Assessment, or S-LCA) (Finkbeiner et al. 2010; Kloepffer 2008). LCSA provides a foundation for sustainable business models (Chen and Holden 2018; Bocken et al. 2014). Most LCSA studies have been conducted in connection with energy and buildings (Wulf et al. 2019). The challenge of connecting social impacts to the functional unit in S-LCA has been a barrier to LCSA development (Lin et al. 2020; Kloepffer 2008), and only a few LCSA studies on agricultural food products have been performed. LCSA on animal food products is still in its infancy, and the lack of a standardized framework for LCSA makes progress challenging. However, there are now a few LCSA publications on animal food products. These work with different frameworks to address some challenges in LCSA, such as lack of data. Valente et al. (2020) performed an LCSA study on pig slaughter using a framework with different system boundaries for E-LCA, S-LCA and Life cycle costing. Chen and Holden (2018) performed an LCSA study on dairy production using a tiered approach, and Scherer et al. (2018) presented a framework for the integration of animal welfare into LCSA that was applicable to cattle, pigs, poultry, salmon, shrimps and insects.

3. Material and methods

The methodology applied, in accordance with ISO 14040 LCA, comprised the following steps:

- 1 Goal and scope definition - We described the goal, scope of study, supply chain system, delimitation, functional units, allocation and impact categories.
- 2 Inventory - We collected data on the four subsystems (farm and feed production, slaughter, wholesaling and retailing, and consumption) for the organic and conventional pork supply chains.
- 3 Impact assessment - We analyzed the environmental, social and economic impacts for the two pork supply chains.
- 4 Interpretation - We presented this step as the result and discussion, and conclusion.

3.1. Goal and scope definition

The goal was to perform a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) of conventional and organic pork supply chains in Sweden,

comparing the two supply chains' environmental, economic and social impacts per 1000 kg pork fork weight as well as per 1000 ha farmland used, and to provide suggestions as to how the overall sustainability of pork production can be improved.

3.1.1. System description

Swedish pork production is divided into two supply chains, conventional and organic, both using the same crossbred breed, the chains' relative volumes are 98% and 2%, respectively (Jordbruksverket 2017). In the organic supply chain, the following requirements are imposed: pigs must have outdoor access all year and grazing during summer, inorganic chemicals in fertilizers and pesticides must not be used in crop production, slaughter pigs should not stay overnight at the slaughterhouse, drivers should use fuel-efficient driving techniques, and electrical energy from renewable sources like wind, solar and hydro should be used (KRAV 2019). In the conventional pork supply chain, by contrast, farmers are not obliged to provide an outdoor area for the pigs, inorganic fertilizer and pesticides are used, slaughter pigs can stay overnight at the slaughterhouse, and any source of electrical energy can be used. Feed ingredients also differ between the two systems, and there are further differences in input resources such as capital, land and labor.

Two typical pig farms were modelled, one conventional and one organic. These represented the production systems in Sweden for both an organic pig farm (according to the KRAV regulation: KRAV 2019) and a conventional one. We assumed that the typical farms were located in Västra Götaland in Sweden. In the conventional pork supply chain the pigs were assumed to be 100% indoors, and in the organic supply chain they were 50% indoors with outdoor access, and 50% outdoor on pasture yearly (Carlsson et al. 2009). We also modelled theoretical slaughterhouses using different sources of electricity. The slaughterhouse in the conventional supply chain used the Swedish electricity mix, whereas the slaughterhouse in the organic supply chain used electricity from renewable energy sources complying with KRAV regulations (KRAV 2019). We modelled the farms using certified conventional soybean in Brazil and KRAV certified organic soybean in China assuming that these meet regulations prohibiting child labor (children under 15 years) and forced labor, and also guarantee normal working hours per week and a fair salary as in Roundtable on Responsible Soy (RTRS 2017) and KRAV (KRAV 2019) certified products.

We assumed feed waste was 2% (Schell et al. 2002) and that food waste as a percentage of what enters each stage was 5% loss at slaughter and meat processing, 4% at retail, and 11% at the consumption stage (FAO 2011). An inventory of the inputs used in crop and feed production, pig production, slaughter, wholesaling and retailing, and consumption was performed. The inventory also included environmental, economic and social data. The environmental data included emissions into soil, air and water. The economic data included full costs for goods purchased at the pig farm, life cycle costs downstream and labor costs. The social data included labor hours spent on the farm working in feed production and pig rearing, and in producing bought-in feed and at the slaughterhouse, people consumption days (i.e. the number of people consuming the functional unit in one day) and pig life days for the pigs at the pig farm and slaughterhouse (i.e. the number of days' pigs live corresponding to the functional unit) (both in line with Zira et al. 2020).

System boundaries

The pork LCA included the following four main subsystems: 1) farm and feed production (crop cultivation, feed production and pig production), 2) slaughter, 3) wholesaling and retailing, and 4) consumption, except for Life cycle costing, which ended at retailing. Inputs included fertilizer, electricity, diesel, tap water, light oil

Fig. 1. The Swedish pork supply chains for conventional and organic production with the four subsystems farm and feed production, slaughter, wholesaling and retailing, and consumption.

and pesticides. The electricity used in the organic supply subsystems was from renewable energy sources (except for the wholesaling and retailing, and consumption subsystems). Farm and feed production included i) the cultivation of the feed crops: conventional soybean without genetic modification in Brazil and organic soybean in China, rapeseed in Denmark, wheat, oats, faba beans and barley grown at the pig farm in Sweden; ii) the production of soybean meal/cake, rapeseed meal/cake and wheat bran; iii) the grinding of wheat, oats, faba beans and barley; iv) the mixing of soybean meal/cake, rapeseed meal/cake and wheat bran with grains produced at the pig farm; and v) pig husbandry: the rearing of sows, gilts and slaughter pigs. Manure management was taken into account via impacts associated with manure storage and application. Slaughter included the stunning, bleeding, scalding, evisceration, splitting and chilling of the carcass as well as meat processing. Wholesaling and retailing included the distribution and sale of pork to consumers. Consumption covered the shopping, preparation and nourishment of people at a household. Transport events were included in the study, with impacts assigned to the goods produced. Truck driving in the organic supply chain was based on fuel-efficient driving techniques (KRAV 2019). The system boundary for both pork supply chains is shown in Fig. 1.

NB: Organic excludes pesticides and inorganic fertilizers as inputs.

3.1.1.1. Delimitation. To simplify the study, farm buildings and machinery were omitted. We assumed that impacts from the produc-

tion of farm buildings were small for the two pork supply chains. Minor feed ingredients such as inorganic minerals, vitamins and crystalline amino acids in diets in the conventional supply chain were not included; nor were pharmaceuticals.

3.1.1.2. Functional units. Two functional units were used in parallel: 1000 kg of cooked bone- and fat-free meat at the consumer's fork and the use of 1000 ha of farmland for pork production.

3.1.2. Allocation

Economic allocation was used for the byproducts soybean oil, rapeseed oil and wheat flour (see Fig. 1). The allocation factors were 0.68 for soymeal/cake (World bank 2020a), 0.26 for rapeseed meal/cake (Soca v1 - Greendelta 2017) and 0.04 for wheat bran (Cederberg and Flysjö 2004). We did not allocate any impacts on lard or other pork byproducts used to make rubber, plastic, softeners, etc. (Mora et al. 2019). Allocating all impact from the pigs to the pork is a simplification, since approximately 6–10% of the total value of slaughtered pigs is related to such byproducts and these make up 25% of the live weight (Martí et al. 2011).

3.1.3. Assessment indicators

Assessment for E-LCA was based on mid-point impact indicators for climate change (GWP100), freshwater eutrophication (FEP), marine eutrophication (MEP), terrestrial acidification (TAP100), fossil depletion (FDP), biodiversity damage potential (BDP), freshwater ecotoxicity (FET), marine ecotoxicity (MET), terrestrial ecotoxicity

(TET), human toxicity (HTP) and land degradation (Soil Carbon Loss - SCL100) (see [section 3.3.1](#)). Life Cycle Costing was based on the impact indicators Value Added (VA)/(Life Cycle Costs (LCC) + labor costs) ratio for the farm, slaughterhouse, and wholesaler and retailer (see [section 3.3.2](#)). S-LCA assessment was based on the indicator Social Risk Time (SRT) for the stakeholders *workers, local community, society, consumers, value chain actors and pigs* (see [section 3.3.3](#)). A list of the topics for social sustainability concerns used in the S-LCA based on the availability of indicators in Soca v.1 ([Greendelta 2017](#)) is shown in Table S1 in the supplementary.

3.1.4. Computation

The environmental and social impacts were computed using OpenLCA 1.10.2 ([Greendelta 2019](#)). Ecoinvent 3.3 (APOS) ([Ecoinvent 2016](#)) was used as a database for inventory data for background processes and characterization, and the Soca v.1 database ([Greendelta 2017](#)) was used for the social impacts. The economic impacts were calculated using Microsoft Excel.

3.2. Life cycle inventory

We conducted an inventory for the four production subsystems. We started with an inventory of inputs to the subsystems, and then made inventories for environmental, economic and social outputs. We assumed the same quantity of inputs per kg pork meat in both supply chains for the slaughter, wholesaling and retailing, and consumption, because the processing and preparation of pork was the same in both systems. The input inventory is shown in Table S2 in the supplementary. Details of the farm and feed production, slaughter, wholesaling and retailing and pork consumption are described below.

3.2.1. Environmental inventory

3.2.1.3. Farm and feed production. Pig production

Pig production was assumed to take place on an integrated pig farm, i.e. one producing both weaners and slaughter pigs. Cross-bred pigs of the same breeds were used in both conventional and organic pork supply chains in the assessment. Gilts were assumed to be sourced from a nucleus herd 200 km from the pig production farm and transported by a 14-tonne truck. The slaughter pigs were produced at the integrated pig farms with the production characteristics shown in [Table 1](#). These figures are the same as those previously used by [Zira et al. \(2020\)](#) for a S-LCA. The electricity use required per sow place per year, and per slaughter pig place per year, was assumed to be 738 kWh ([Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län 2018a](#); [Edström et al. 2005](#)) and 62 kWh ([Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län 2018a](#)), respectively.

For the organic pork supply chain, 20% grass-clover leys (according to KRAV regulations) was included in the calculation of land use to assess biodiversity impacts and soil carbon loss. The inventory for environmental data is presented in [Table S3-S5](#) in the supplementary.

Enteric methane emissions for pork were calculated assuming emissions of 1.5 kg per pig per year ([IPCC 2019a](#)). Methane emissions from manure storage were calculated based on volatile solids (VS), methane generation potential (B_0) and the methane conversion factor (MCF) for Sweden. In the organic pork supply chain VS were calculated to be 410 kg per sow place and year, and 150 kg per slaughter pig place and year. In the conventional pork supply chain VS were assumed to be 320 kg per sow place and year, and 120 kg per slaughter pig place and year. In both cases, a digestibility value of 75%, urinary energy value of 2% and ash value of 5% were applied ([Berglund et al. 2013](#); [IPCC 2006a](#)). B_0 was assumed to be 0.45 kg/kg VS for all pigs ([IPCC 2019a](#)). It was assumed that the liquid manure system was used in the conventional pork supply chain, and that the solid manure system was used in the or-

ganic pork supply chain. MCF was set at 3.5% for pigs in the conventional supply chain to reflect the use of a slurry manure management system ([Lantz and Björnsson 2016](#)). The MCF for the pigs in the organic pork supply chain was set at 2% ([Berglund 2017](#)) for pig housing to reflect the use of a solid manure management system there, and at 1% for outdoor/grazing ([Ingela Löfqvist Hushållningssällskapet personal communication 2020](#)).

For direct nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions from manure storage, we estimated 0.005 kg N_2O -N/kg nitrogen (N) for N deposited in the slurry for pigs in the conventional pork supply chain and 0.010 kg N_2O -N/kg N for N deposited in solid manure for pigs in the organic pork supply chain with solid manure management ([IPCC 2019a](#)). The emission factors for indirect N_2O emissions are presented in [Table 4](#). Ammonia emissions during housing are influenced by the manure system used; a liquid manure system has more emissions than a solid system. Ammonia emissions for pig housing were assumed to be 14% of the N that is excreted by pigs in the conventional pork supply chain and 10% in the organic pork supply chain ([Berglund 2017](#)). Emissions from storage were assumed to be 10% of the N stored in the storage facility in the conventional pork supply chain and 20% in the organic pork supply chain due to the dilution effects of water in liquid manure ([Berglund 2017](#)). The N balance and fluxes from which the emissions were calculated are shown in [Tables S4 and S5](#) in the supplementary and the other emission factors used are shown in [Table 4](#).

Crop and feed production

The diets consisted of seven main ingredients, as shown in [Table 2](#). We left out agri-byproducts from the food and energy industry because their proportion in the pig diets varies between farms and over time, ranging from non-use to approximately 31 kg of total feed intake of a slaughter pig on dry matter basis ([RISE 2020](#)), depending on availability. We replaced agri-byproducts with oilseed meals and faba beans to balance the nutrient requirements of the animals. The cereal ingredients and faba beans were assumed to be produced at the pig farm in Sweden, whereas soybean and rapeseed meal and cake were taken to be imported. In the organic pork supply chain, we included the use of forage, as this is a requirement imposed by the organic regulations ([KRAV 2019](#)); the diet for a sow included 200 kg forage dry matter per year and the diet for a slaughter pig included 20 kg dry matter per animal lifetime ([Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län 2018b](#)). Input requirements for crop production are shown in [Table 3](#) ([Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län 2018a](#); [2018b](#)). The feed intake for pigs in the organic pork supply chain, especially sows, was larger than it was in the conventional pork supply chain because organic sows require more energy for thermoregulation and have heightened locomotion and a longer lactation period ([Eskildsen et al. 2020](#)).

Pesticides including herbicides, insecticides, molluscicide and fungicides are used for crop production in the conventional pork supply chain. The total mass of the active ingredients is shown in [Table 3](#). Quantities of individual pesticides per hectare per feed crop ([Nordborg et al. 2017](#)) are shown in [Table S6](#) in the supplementary.

We estimated emissions of N compounds from N application using the ([IPCC 2019b](#); [2019c](#)) emission factors summarized in [Table 4](#). N in crop residues was calculated using [IPCC \(2019b\)](#) formulas. Carbon dioxide emissions from lime applications were assumed to be 12% of the lime applied ([IPCC 2006b](#)).

For conventional production, we assumed that ammonium nitrate was used as the nitrogen source, potash as potassium source and single super phosphate as the phosphorous source to retrieve impacts from fertilizer production from Ecoinvent 3.3 for each region ([Ecoinvent 2016](#)). Modern fertilizer plants in Europe are now equipped with N_2O reduction technology and emissions from ammonium nitrate production are 3.5–3.6 kg CO_2 eq per

Table 1
The characteristics of the two average pig farms in Sweden.

	Conventional	Organic	Source
<i>Sow</i>			
Number of litters/sow per year	2.3	2.1	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018); Agriculture Horticulture Development Board (2017)
Live born piglets per litter	14.6	12.4	Gård and Djurhålsan (2017); Agriwise (2018)
Mean daily weight gain pre weaning nursery (kg/d)	0.3	0.3	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Weaning age (days)	33	42	Ingvar Eriksson pers comm (2019); Agriculture Horticulture Development Board (2017)
Mortality piglets nursery (% of total of live born pigs)	18	21	Gård and Djurhålsan (2017)
Piglets live weight at weaning (kg)	10	13	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018); Agriculture Horticulture Development Board (2017)
Mortality sows (%)	7	7	Ingvar Eriksson Gård djurhålsan pers comm (2019)
Culled sows in % of total number of annual sows	50	40	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Gilt age at first farrowing (days)	354	367	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Gilt weight at first insemination (kg)	140	140	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Mean sow weight (kg)	240	240	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
<i>Growing and finishing pig</i>			
Mean daily weight gain 11–35kg weaners (kg/day)	0.60	0.57	Ingvar Eriksson pers comm (2019)
Post weaning nursing period (days)	42	38.5	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Mean daily weight gain 36–60kg growers (kg/day)	0.68	0.65	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Growing period (days)	37	38	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Mean daily weight gain 61–110kg finishers (kg/day)	0.9	0.85	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Finishing period (days)	67	68	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018)
Mortality weaners (% of total number of weaners)	2	4	Ingvar Eriksson pers comm (2019)
Mortality growing pigs (% of total number of growers)	1.0	1.9	Ingvar Eriksson pers comm (2019)
Mortality finishers (% of total number of finishers)	1.8	1.6	Ingvar Eriksson pers comm (2019); Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018); Agriwise (2018)
Live weight at slaughter (kg)	124	120	Nils Lundeheim pers comm (2018); Ingvar Eriksson pers comm (2019)

Note: Data from Zira et al. (2020 p 1961)

Table 2
The pork supply chains' feed ingredients as a percentage of raw feed diet and the feed intake in kg.

	Dry sow		Lactating sow		Piglet		Slaughter pig	
	Conventional	Organic	Conventional	Organic	Conventional	Organic	Conventional	Organic
Wheat, %	40	34	44	34	43	34	42	27
Barley, %	29	34	37	34	38	34	32	27
Oats, %	17	21	5	5	8	5	5.3	0
Wheat bran, %	3.4	6.5	3.4	6	0	6	1.1	14
Faba bean, %	1	0	0	0	1	0	11	19
Rapeseed ¹ , %	3	1	3	1	0	1	4.6	1
Soybean ² , %	6.6	3.5	6.9	20	10	20	4	12
Feed intake (kg)	840 ³	880 ³	710 ³	890 ³	47 ⁴	46 ⁴	250 ⁴	270 ⁴

Diets in the conventional pork supply chain based on Cederberg et al. (2009) and RISE (2020); modified to reflect current conventional pig feed diets not including agri-byproducts

Diets in the organic pork supply chain (Ingela Löfqvist Hushållningssällskapet personal communication 2020). In organic production pigs are also fed with forage (not presented in the table)

¹ Rape meal in the conventional supply chain and rape cake in the organic supply chain

² Soybean meal in the conventional supply chain and soybean cake in the organic supply chain

³ Feed per sow per year

⁴ Feed per pig per life time

kg N in ammonium nitrate (Yara 2020; Berglund 2017). We assumed that the ammonium nitrate fertilizer on the Swedish market had an average 5.0 kg CO₂ eq per kg N in ammonium nitrate (Greppa näringen 2011) because imports from old plants are also used. We assumed phosphorous leaching from crop fields to be 0.72 kg/ha/year for the farm, the average in Västra Götaland (Johnsson et al. 2019), 3 kg/ha/year in Brazil (Cederberg and Flysjö 2004), 2.2 kg/ha/year in China (Li et al. 2015) and 0.5 kg/ha/year in Denmark (Heckrath et al. 2005).

3.2.1.4. Slaughter. It was assumed that live pigs were transported 50 km from the farm by a 16-tonne truck. At the slaughter sub-

system, the pigs were slaughtered and the carcasses were cut, chilled and packaged. Pig carcasses are often used to produce various pork products (e.g. smoked pork, cooked sausages and fermented sausages), but for simplicity we assumed that all meat was sold as fresh raw meat in units of 500 g pork cuts. The pork was packaged in Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) meat trays weighing 18.43 g each, with a volume of 1 liter (Maga et al. 2019). In terms of energy use, 797 kWh of electricity and 317 kWh oil was assumed to be required per 1000 kg live weight pigs (Edström et al. 2005). Further, it was assumed that 80 g of nitrogen and 8 g of phosphorous per slaughter pig were emitted into water (Naturvårdsverket 2009). Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

Table 3
Yields and inputs in conventional (Conv.) and organic (Org.) crop production.

Origin	Soybean		Wheat		Oats		Faba beans		Barley		Rapeseed	
	Conv. Brazil	Org. China	Conv. Sweden	Org. Sweden	Conv. Denmark	Org. Denmark						
Seed (kg/ha)	56 ⁴	55 ⁷	210 ⁸	230 ⁹	190 ⁸	230 ⁹	280 ⁸	280 ⁹	180 ⁸	210 ⁹	5 ⁸	5 ⁹
N applied (kg/ha)	8 ²	1.5 ³	155 ⁸	80 ⁹	90 ⁸	38 ⁹	0 ⁸	0 ⁹	115 ⁸	80 ⁹	205 ⁸	140 ⁹
P applied (kg/ha)	31 ²	2.3 ³	18 ⁸	11 ⁹	17 ⁸	8 ⁹	9 ⁸	7.5 ⁹	12 ⁸	10 ⁹	25 ⁸	52.5 ⁹
K applied (kg/ha)	57 ¹¹	7.5 ³	20 ⁸	4 ⁹	13 ⁸	2 ⁹	15 ⁸	10 ⁹	10 ⁸	2 ⁹	25 ⁸	87.5 ⁹
Lime (kg/ha)	0	0	150 ⁸	100 ⁹	150 ⁸	100 ⁹						
Diesel (liter/ha)	65 ⁴	35 ⁷	86 ⁸	105 ⁹	77 ⁸	108 ⁹	79 ⁸	82 ⁹	77 ⁸	108 ⁹	86 ⁸	87 ⁹
Yield (kg/ha)	3000 ⁴	2800 ⁷	7000 ⁸	4200 ⁹	5500 ⁸	3500 ⁹	3000 ⁸	2300 ⁹	5000 ⁸	4000 ⁹	4000 ⁸	3500 ⁹
Pesticides (g active ingredient/ha)	2200 ¹⁰	0 ³	500 ¹⁰	0 ⁹	520 ¹⁰	0 ⁹	630 ¹⁰	0 ⁹	280 ¹⁰	0 ⁹	1600 ¹⁰	0 ⁹
Work time (hours/ha)	7.5 ⁴	326.0 ⁷	5.2 ⁸	5.6 ⁹	4.3 ⁸	5.3 ⁹	5.0 ⁸	6.2 ⁹	5.3 ⁸	6.4 ⁹	5.3 ⁸	5.5 ⁹
Electricity drying (kWh/ha)	0 ³	0 ³	98 ²	59 ²	77 ²	49 ²	42 ²	32 ²	77 ²	56 ²	56 ²	49 ²
Oil drying (MJ/ha)	780 ²	840 ³	2100 ²	1260 ²	1650 ²	1050 ²	900 ²	690 ²	1650 ²	1200 ²	1200 ²	1050 ²

¹ Agriwise (2018)

²Organic requires low energy for drying as a result of low yields per hectare. Cederberg and Flysjö (2004); ³Cederberg et al. (2011); ⁴Cremaschi et al. (2015)

⁵HIR Malmöhus (2015)

⁶Jordbruksverket 2019

⁷Knudsen et al. (2010)

⁸Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län (2018a)

⁹Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län (2018b)

¹⁰Nordborg et al. (2017)

¹¹SOCA v.1 (Greendelta 2017)

Table 4

The emission factors for ammonia (NH₃), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and nitrogen (N) leached from the soil from synthetic fertilizers and bio fertilizers, slurry spreading and excreta from grazing pigs.

Emission factors	kg (NH ₃ -N)/kg N	kg (NO _x -N)/kg N	kg N ₂ O-N/kg N (direct)	kg N ₂ O-N/kg N (indirect)	kg N leached/kg N
Synthetic fertilizer (ammonium nitrate)	0.03	0.029	0.01	0.01 (NH ₃) + 0.011 (N leaching)	0.24
Bio fertilizer and slurry spreading	0.197	0.015	0.01	0.01 (NH ₃) + 0.011 (N leaching)	0.24
Crop residues	0.197	0.015	0.01	0.01 (NH ₃) + 0.011 (N leaching)	0.24
Excreta from grazing pigs	0.197	0.015	0.004	0.01 (NH ₃) + 0.011 (N leaching)	0.24

Note: Data from IPCC (2019c)

is a measure of the oxygen consumed by water due to bacterial activity. The discharge of slaughterhouse waste results in increased demand for oxygen by water, which was assumed to be 1800 g per slaughter pig (Naturvårdsverket 2009). We assumed that a slaughterhouse in Sweden uses 0.45 m³ water for a pig weighing 120 kg liveweight (Naturvårdsverket 2009).

It was assumed that the meat was transported 50 km from the slaughterhouse to the distribution point in a refrigerated truck with carbon dioxide refrigeration. Emissions and resource use for 1000 kg of pork fork weight were retrieved from Ecoinvent 3.3 (Ecoinvent 2016).

3.2.1.5. Wholesaling and retailing. It was assumed that pork from the slaughterhouse was sold to a vertically integrated retailer (i.e. wholesaling and retailing were done by the same actor), that 10 days would elapse between slaughter and consumer purchase, and that the meat was transported 50 km in a truck with carbon dioxide refrigeration from the distribution point to the retail store. The electricity required for meat storage was set at 11.7 kWh per m³ (Carlsson-Kanyama 1999). We also assumed that pork would require 2.23 m³ of space per tonne during transportation and storage (Baker et al. 2012). Emissions and resource use for transportation were calculated per tonne km using emission factors retrieved from Ecoinvent 3.3 (Ecoinvent 2016).

3.2.1.6. Consumption. The cooked fork weight of pork was assumed to correspond to 36% of the live weight of the slaughtered pigs (Åsa Öberg Jordbruksverket personal communication 2020). We assumed that consumers need to travel 200 km per 1000 kg of pork live weight (retail weight 59% of live weight) (Edström et al. 2005),

and that each consumer used a small petrol (1.6 liter engine capacity) car for shopping. We also assumed that 195 kWh of electricity would be used for 1000 kg pork live weight (590 kg of pork retail weight) in cooking and refrigeration (Edström et al. 2005), together with 5 kg of water to wash dishes for every 1 kg pork fork weight prepared. The emissions to air and water and resource use were calculated using emission factors from Ecoinvent 3.3 (Ecoinvent 2016).

3.2.2. Economic inventory

Costs for the inputs required to produce 1000 kg of pork fork weight were calculated based on the input requirements in the four subsystems and each input's unit cost (see Table S7 in the supplementary). The costs include the operational costs and are presented in Table S8 in the supplementary. For labor costs, we multiplied the cost of labor (salary and social benefits) per hour, i.e. 260 SEK per hour for farm labor, which was indexed from 206 SEK in 2012 (LRF 2012) to the cost in 2017 and 370 SEK per hour for the slaughterhouse, wholesaler and retailer as the average labor cost per hour in 2017 (Ekonomifakta 2020) by the work hours calculated for crop production from Table 3 and pig production work hours described in section 3.2.3.

3.2.3. Social inventory

Social Risk Time (SRT), an indicator of risk used in an S-LCA, is calculated based on i) the activity variable (T), and ii) the Social Risk (SR) (Greendelta 2017) – see section 3.3.3. For the stakeholders workers, value chain actors, local community and society the activity variable was the work hours needed either to produce 1000 kg pork fork weight or to produce pork from 1000 hectares of

land. The activity variables were used as input in Soca v1. The Soca database includes a range of indicators to capture social impacts of different sectors on different stakeholders. Values for the indicators are collected from primary or secondary sources for the list of social sustainability concerns shown in Table S1 (Greendelta 2017). For example, the percentage of children in employment, is an inventory indicator for the stakeholder *workers*. Social Risk is the risk assigned to the inventory indicator. The Social Risk value indicates the potential negative social impacts based on a reference scale (from 0 – no risk, to 100 – very high risk). Hence, it provides a way of normalizing indicator values so that social impacts can be aggregated. In most cases, the reference scale has six performance points: no risk (0), very low risk (0.01), low risk (0.1), medium risk (1), high risk (10) and very high risk (100) (Greendelta 2017). Continuing with our earlier example (% of children in employment), the value in Brazil's soybean sector was 4.2% in Soca v.1 (Green Delta 2017). This meant that the Social Risk (SR) was low and equal to 0.1, because Soca v.1 defines low risk when the percentage of children in employment varies between 2.5 and 5 (Greendelta 2017). We used the Soca v.1 database for the SR and inventory indicators for the stakeholders *workers*, *local community*, *society* and *value chain actors*. For the activity variable on the farm, we used work hours spent in crop production in Table 3. To calculate the work hours for pig production, we assumed 15 hours per sow and year and 0.2 hours per slaughter pig in the conventional pork supply chain (Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län 2018a) and 33 hours per sow and year and 0.8 hours per slaughter pig in the organic pork supply chain (Länsstyrelsen Västra Götalands län 2018b). For the slaughterhouse, the total labor hours for the production of the retail weight that results in 1000 kg pork fork weight were assumed to be 2.7 hours (Zira et al. 2020). We assumed that work hours were 1 hour per 1000 kg pork fork weight for the wholesaler and retailer, because it was difficult to ascertain actual time given the huge assortment of goods handled at wholesale and in the supermarket.

The activity variables for *pigs* and *consumers* were calculated (see Table S9 in the supplementary) and used as input in the calculation of social impact in Excel. The activity variable for pigs was pig life days calculated as the product of the number of pigs required to produce the functional unit and number of life days on the farm and at the slaughterhouse. The activity variable for *consumers* was people consumption days, which is the quotient of the functional unit (1000 kg pork fork weight), and average pork consumption per capita per day in Sweden, which is 40 g. (Åsa Öberg Jordbruksverket personal communication 2020; Zira et al. 2020). Social impacts on *pigs* and *consumers* could not be calculated in Soca (Greendelta 2017) as the indicators for these were not present in Soca. We, therefore, used inventory indicators (see column *Inventory indicators for each subsystem and reference scale*) and Social Risk values (see column *Conventional SR = z* and *Organic SR = z*) in Table S10-S12 in the Supplementary (same as in Zira et al. (2020)), but the performance reference scales were aligned with those in Soca to calculate social risk using the method in Zira et al. (2020). Soca has data for 189 countries in it, close to 15,000 sectors, detailed and differentiated by their commodities and industries. We created sectors for the wheat bran, slaughterhouse, wholesaler, retailer and consumers because these did not exist in Soca. We also created a sector for soybean production in China, adjusting the social parameters to suit Chinese production conditions. For the soybean production sector in Brazil, we used the existing sector in Soca. We also used existing sectors in Europe for cereal crops, faba bean, rapeseed, rapeseed meal, soybean meal expeller and mechanical extraction methods, ammonia nitrate, single super phosphate, potash, pesticides, tap water, light oil and diesel, and for pig housing. When data from Sweden was missing in Soca, we used the country most similar in production and structure (e.g. for ce-

real crops we used Germany). We used the Swedish electricity mix for electricity supplies in Sweden in the conventional pork supply chain and for the wholesaler, retailer and consumers in the organic pork supply chain. For electricity in the organic pork supply chain, we used Norway's electricity mix, because Norway has the highest proportion of renewable electricity in its electricity mix in the world, 96.54% (Global Petrol Prices 2020). We used Swedish solar electricity for pig housing in the organic pork supply chain. We adjusted inputs and outputs for crops, pig production, slaughter, wholesaling and retailing and consumer according to our inventory data from Sweden.

3.3. Impact assessment

We used mid-point impacts in the characterization of the environmental and social indicators. This section gives a detailed description of the characterization methods for environmental, economic and social impacts.

3.3.1. Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

Recipe midpoint 2016 (H) V1.13 was used for characterization (Goedkoop et al. 2013). The environmental impacts of pork production are a result of emissions of environmentally damaging compounds into soil, water and/or air, as well as use of resources such as land and fossil resources. We analyzed contribution to climate change (the global increase in temperature due to greenhouse gases) as Global Warming Potential over 100 years, including feedback loops (IPCC 2013). Eutrophication, i.e. the pollution state of aquatic ecosystems leading to increased biomass growth, was characterized as freshwater eutrophication (FEP) and marine eutrophication (MEP). Acidification, i.e. the decrease in pH values in the natural environment, was characterized as terrestrial acidification (TAP100). Fossil resource depletion, i.e. the reduction in the quantity of fossil resources, was characterized as fossil depletion (FDP). See Goedkoop et al. (2013) for descriptions of FEP, MEP, TAP100 and FDP in Recipe midpoint 2016 (H) V1.13. We analyzed the impact categories listed above because these are the most important impacts for pork (Noya et al. 2017; Reckmann et al. 2012). We also included potential species loss, marine, freshwater, terrestrial and human ecotoxicity, and agricultural land degradation, because these are important factors in the comparison of conventional and organic product supply chains (Van der Werf et al. 2020). Potential species loss, i.e. the difference in species richness between a reference ecosystem over time and an area with a given land use type, was characterized as Biodiversity Damage Potential (BDP) (Knudsen et al. 2017). BDP for a supply chain was the sum of the area required for cropping, where BDP for crop production was a product of the characterization factor for crop production multiplied by time and area used for crop production. The characterization factors were derived by dividing the species richness for the given land use by the reference ecosystem's species richness. Characterization factors relating to the potentially damaged fraction of plant species per square meter for different types of land uses are shown in Table S18 in the supplementary. The model has several limitations, e.g. it does not incorporate urban land use, and the biodiversity of species such as reptiles, mammals and birds is measured only indirectly.

Environmental toxicity (the negative effects of chemicals on organisms in their natural environments) was included as FET, MET, TET and HTP. Terrestrial ecotoxicity is dominated by the impacts of agricultural soil pesticide emissions (Borrion et al. 2012). By contrast, freshwater ecotoxicity is dominated by impacts from emissions of pesticide applied to agricultural soil and heavy metals leaked into freshwater bodies (Nemecek et al. 2016). Marine ecotoxicity is dominated by impacts of heavy metals emissions into

marine water bodies (Borrion et al. 2012). With regards to toxicity in the human environment, human toxicity (carcinogenic) deals with carcinogenic substances using the World Health Organization evaluation of carcinogenic substances. The mid-point characterization factors for all the ecotoxicity indicators and human toxicity are 1.4 dichlorobenzene equivalents. In other words, the effects of substances emitted are divided by the effects of the chemical 1,4-dichlorobenzene (DCB), which is used as a reference (Goedkoop et al. 2013).

Agricultural land degradation, captured here by gain/loss of soil organic carbon, was included as soil carbon changes over 100 years in accordance with the Introductory Carbon Balance Method (ICBM) presented in Moberg et al. (2019). We used the ICBM method in our assessment of soil carbon changes. Thus we calculated the amount of carbon the soil stores, or loses, until it reaches a steady state when cereals, legumes, rapeseed and grass-clover ley are each cultivated on a hectare of land and then subtracted the steady state soil carbon amount from 100 tonnes carbon per ha, which is the reference carbon content in Swedish soils. The difference was then divided over a period of 100 years to obtain an annual change, i.e. the potential annual soil carbon changes per ha. Based on this it was assumed that cereals had a loss of 150 kg carbon per year per hectare, that soybeans and faba beans had each a loss of 190 kg carbon per year per hectare, and that rapeseed had a loss of 160 kg carbon per year per hectare. Grass-clover mixture production was assumed to lead to carbon capture of 270 kg carbon per year per hectare (Moberg et al. 2019). The land used for the different crops is shown in Table S18 in the Supplementary Material. This is a simplified assessment of soil carbon that does not account for differences in crop yields and the amount of manure between the two systems.

3.3.2. Life Cycle Costing

We used the method of Life Cycle Costing given by Konstantas et al. (2019). This was adjusted to include labor costs as outlined in section 3.2.2, as there is a large difference in the farm's labor requirements in conventional and organic pork supply chains, as shown in Table 3 and section 3.2.1. Under LCC we included operational costs excluding wages, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes, and VA was then the amount that can be used for these excluded costs thus calculated as the difference between the product price and the LCC for each supply chain stage (Konstantas et al. 2020, 2019). The impact indicator used to investigate economic sustainability was the VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for each stage in the supply chain, i.e. farm, slaughterhouse, and wholesaler and retailer. The VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio indicates whether the supply chain actor has a potentially viable business. This is not relevant for a consumer, and therefore we omitted consumers from the life cycle costing. The VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio represents the value created at that particular stage in the chain. A higher VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio is desirable and means more value is created by a supply chain actor.

3.3.2.7. Life Cycle Costs. These costs were calculated according to Konstantas et al. (2019) as follows:

$$LCC_P = CRM + CMA_P + CTR_P \quad (1)$$

$$LCC_S = CPA_S + CO_S + CTR_S \quad (2)$$

$$LCC_{W/R} = CD_{W/R} + CRE_{W/R} + CTR_{W/R} \quad (3)$$

where CRM denotes the costs of raw materials (fertilizer, seed, pesticides, diesel etc.),

CMA_P the costs of product manufacturing at the farm (excluding wages, salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes),

CTR_P the costs of transport for the farmer,

CPA_S the costs of packaging for the slaughterhouse,

CO_S the costs of operating the slaughterhouse (excluding salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes),

CTR_S the costs of transport for the slaughterhouse,

$CD_{W/R}$ the costs of distribution for the wholesaler and retailer (excluding salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes),

$CRE_{W/R}$ the costs of retailing for the wholesaler and retailer (excluding salaries, interest, depreciation, rent, and taxes),

$CTR_{W/R}$ the costs of transport for the wholesaler and retailer,

VA can be defined in more than one way. In the LCC approach by Konstantas et al. (2019) that we follow, VA is the benefit to a specific value chain actor arising from the difference between the price and the input costs of production. From another perspective, value added in a business can be described as the surplus beyond the customers' expectations and the gain in a company's share value, but this was not the perspective taken in our study.

3.3.3. Social Life Cycle Assessment

We used Social Risk Time (SRT) for all stakeholders as an impact indicator. The formula for calculating SRT is shown in equation (4).

$$SRT_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^J (T_{ijk} * SR_{ijk}) \quad (4)$$

Where i denotes the stakeholder (e.g. workers), j denotes the inventory indicator (e.g. fair salary for workers), k denotes the subsystem (e.g. slaughterhouse) and SRT denotes Social Risk Time for stakeholder i , T_{ijk} denotes the activity variable for stakeholder i for indicator j and subsystem k and SR_{ijk} denotes the Social Risk for stakeholder i for indicator j and subsystem k . The lower the SRT, the less risk there is of negative social impacts. Hence, low SRT is better when we are comparing two supply chains.

3.3.4. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

The organic pork supply chain's environmental, economic and social indicators were compared with those in the conventional pork supply chain using Relative Sustainability Points (RSP). An RSP score below 0.5 for the organic pork supply chain means that the chain is performing better than the conventional pork supply chain for the indicator in question, and an RSP score above 0.5 indicates the opposite. The RSP score for an indicator ranges from 0-1. Formulas (5) and (6) were used to calculate RSP: when a higher value for an indicator reflects a more negative impact, for example GWP100, and

$$RSP = 1 - EXP(LN(0.5) * IND_{org}/IND_{conv}) \quad (5)$$

when a lower value for an indicator reflects a more negative impact of an indicator, for example VA/(LCC + labor costs)

$$RSP = EXP(LN(0.5) * IND_{org}/IND_{conv}) \quad (6)$$

where IND_{org} and IND_{conv} are the environmental, economic or social indicator values for organic and conventional pork production, respectively.

3.3.5. Sensitivity Analysis

We carried out twelve sensitivity analyses using the product functional unit: i) inclusion of agri-byproducts as feed, ii) change in crop yields, iii) change of nitrogen leaching during grazing, iv) change in soil carbon method, v) change of fuel type used in the car used by the consumer, vi) change in the biodiversity model, vii) change in the mineral fertilizer production emission factor, viii) access to the outdoor environment in the conventional system, ix)

change of country producing soybean, x) increase or decrease in the international market price of soybean, xi) change in the producer price for slaughter pigs and xii) increase in salary by 5% on the farm. For the sensitivity analyses, a change in crop yields and pigs' access to the outdoor was carried out across all the three sustainability pillars.

In the diet for slaughter pigs, we did not consider the use of agri-byproducts from the food and energy industry (e.g. wheat distillers can be used in conventional pig diets as a protein source, especially for slaughter pigs). For the environmental impacts per unit product, we conducted sensitivity analyses of the effect of inclusion of 31 kg dry matter of agri-byproducts from the food and energy industry in the total feed intake of a slaughter pig between 30 kg and the slaughter weight by substituting 80% of the soybean, 77% of the rapeseed and 44% of the faba bean used. We assumed that the agri-byproducts came free from environmental burden, i.e. their environmental impact was zero. We also examined the effect of a $\pm 20\%$ higher yield change for one crop at a time and a change to the lowest value of nitrogen leaching during grazing described in IPCC (2019c).

Soil carbon change is an indicator of soil quality, but it is difficult to assess because it depends on climate, on soil type and on agricultural land-use practices. We used a different model, supplied by the IPCC to be used in national greenhouse gas inventories (IPCC 2019b), which is based on multiplication of the reference carbon stock with the negative carbon stock change factors from land use, management factors and inputs, and thereafter added the amount of carbon stored to the reference stock, to see how the results would be affected by a change in the model. The consumer's car was switched from one using a fossil fuel to one running on electricity to analyze the change in impacts, since an electric car was assumed to be more environment-friendly than an internal combustion engine car. An alternative biodiversity model, proposed by Chaudhary and Brooks (2018), was used, because it assesses biodiversity for reptiles, mammals and birds, tracking potential species loss directly and not indirectly as the model by Knudsen et al. (2017). However, the Chaudhary and Brooks (2018) model is set on a larger spatial scale and thus does not specifically capture the differences in organic and conventional production.

About 66% of nitric acid plants in Europe have low-temperature tail-gases in the production process. This rules out high-temperature-dependent decomposition of nitrous oxide (IPCC 2006c). However, modern plants using catalytic cleansing technology, which cuts up to 90% of nitrous oxide emissions in nitric acid production, have low greenhouse gas emissions for ammonium nitrate fertilizer manufacturing (3.5–3.6 kg CO₂ eq per kg N in ammonium nitrate (Yara 2020; Berglund 2017)) than the average of ammonium nitrate on the Swedish market (5 kg CO₂ eq per kg N in ammonium nitrate (Greppa näringen 2011)). We therefore analyzed the change to entire use of ammonium nitrate from a modern plant.

In our sensitivity analyses for the social impacts we asked whether importing soybean from a European country would affect the results. The change in social impacts of allowing pigs access to the outdoor environment were studied for the conventional supply chain.

We carried out sensitivity analyses of the economic impacts of a change in soy prices i.e. $\pm 32\%$ change according to the changes in the last five years (World bank 2020a), $\pm 20\%$ change in pork producer price, also according to changes in the last five years (Jordbruksverket 2020), $\pm 20\%$ change in crop yields and access to the outdoor environment for the product indicators, all in the same fashion as the environmental and social impacts. We also performed a sensitivity analysis for a 5% increase in salary on the

farm and also a total removal of labor costs from VA/(LCC + labor ratio).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Environmental Life Cycle Assessment

The environmental impacts per 1000 kg pork fork weight showed that the conventional pork supply chain had 7–23% lower environmental impacts than the organic pork supply chain for FEP, MEP, TAP100 and FDP. The organic pork supply chain had 4–54% lower environmental impacts than the conventional pork supply chain for BDP, FET, MET, TET, HTP and SCL100. GWP was the same for both supply chains. Results of the environmental analysis are shown in Table 5. When the environmental impacts were expressed per 1000 ha of farmland used, the organic pork supply chain had 38–80% lower environmental impacts than the conventional pork supply chain in all impact categories. The lower environmental impacts in organic production per area are due to fact that organic agriculture uses less inputs per hectare besides fuel. In the organic supply chain, the use of renewable sources of electricity such as wind, solar and hydro, fuel-efficient driving techniques and non-use of inorganic fertilizers and pesticides did not offset the increased environmental impacts created by lower yields and more polluting manure handling for the indicators FEP, MEP, TAP100 and FDP. However, as a result of the avoidance of synthetic pesticide use in organic production the toxicity indicators (FET, MET, TET and HTP) were lower in organic production both per kg product and per hectare.

Feed production substantially influences most of the environmental impacts on the two pork supply chains and therefore it is a hotspot. With GWP100, for example, the biggest impact factor was feed production (i.e. crop inputs, cultivation and processing), which was 67% for the conventional pork supply chain and 68% for the organic pork supply chain, as shown in Fig. S1 in the supplementary. These results are consistent with conclusions from previous European studies reporting that feed production contributed between 50% and 85% of the impacts of GWP100 in pork production (Six et al. 2017; González-García et al. 2015; Reckmann et al. 2013; Pelletier et al. 2010; Dalgaard et al. 2007). By contrast, post-farm stages (slaughter, wholesaler and retailer, and storage and preparation by the consumer) contributed only 9% and 8% to total GWP100 in conventional and organic pork supply chains, respectively.

GWP had the same value for both pork supply chains because the low yields in crop production, high feed intake by pigs and higher use of diesel for mechanical operation in crop production in the organic pork supply chain annulled the avoided emissions from the production of inorganic fertilizers.

The organic pork supply chain exhibited lower impacts for FET, MET, TET and HTP because no pesticides were used in it for crop production. However, both pork supply chains led to emissions of toxic metals such as copper, nickel, chrome and zinc caused by the mining of raw minerals (e.g. the copper used for electricity generation and transmission). Heavy metals such as cadmium, similarly, were emitted in deposition, with the organic supply chain having slightly higher levels of deposition as a result of its greater land use. Soil liming products used in both pork supply chains also contributed heavy metals such as cadmium in the soil.

The lower BDP in the organic pork supply chain can be explained by lower biodiversity losses on the organic cropland (Table S18). This is in line with previous research, which has found, on average, a 30–50% higher plant species richness in organic farming systems than in conventional farming systems (Tuck et al. 2014; Bengtsson et al. 2005). However, if the model described by Chaudhary and Brooks (2018) is applied, the conventional pork supply chain performs better than its organic counterpart in poten-

Table 5

Environmental impacts for production of 1000 kg pork fork weight and 1000 ha of farmland in the pork supply chains (higher of the two marked in bold).

Impact category	Units	Impacts per 1000 kg pork		Impacts per 1000 ha farmland	
		Conventional	Organic	Conventional	Organic
Global warming potential 100	kg CO ₂ eq	7 100	7 100	3 900 000	1 800 000
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	2.7	3.1	1 500	800
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	110	130	61 000	33 000
Terrestrial acidification 100	kg SO ₂ eq	200	260	110 000	68 000
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq	1 300	1 400	720 000	360 000
Biodiversity damage potential	Potential disappeared fraction	12 000	9 000	6 700 000	2 300 000
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1.4 DCB eq	85	80	47 000	21 000
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1.4 DCB eq	77	74	43 000	19 000
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1.4 DCB eq	10	4.6	5 500	1 100
Human toxicity potential	kg 1.4 DCB eq	2 000	1 700	1 100 000	430 000
Soil Carbon loss 100	tonne carbon	0.29	0.26	160	66

GWP100 does not include emissions associated with soil carbon losses

tial biodiversity loss, because there is less difference in characterization factors between the different land-use management practices in this model. The model variance here is a result of lower resolution in Chaudhary and Brooks (2018) that does not capture the difference between organic and conventional land use. This is a valuable reminder of the significant influence of the method used to assess impacts of biodiversity and the need for further research in this area.

The organic pork supply chain used twice as much land at the farm, as shown in Table S18 in the supplementary. All the land used for feed production at the farm in the conventional pork supply chain was for annual crop production, whereas this was 80% in the organic pork supply chain, with the remaining 20% being used for grass-clover leys in rotation. The carbon sequestering from the grass-clover leys compensated for the cropping's carbon loss per kg of meat. Soil carbon changes are difficult to capture and model, as they are highly site-specific and influenced by a range of factors that are seldom available for all the land involved in the supply chain (e.g. different fields at the farm and fields used for imported feed). In the soil model used here (ICBM), the soil carbon changes for different crops can be calculated. This is not possible using the IPCC model owing to the blanket stock change factors for all cropping. The IPCC model shows that SCL was 0.55 tonnes carbon per 1000 kg pork fork weight in the conventional pork supply chain and 0.88 tonnes carbon per 1000 kg pork fork weight in the organic pork supply chain. The conventional pork supply chain performs better than its organic counterpart. The results also heavily depend on the proportions of annual crops and leys. Without the 20% ley in crop rotations the organic pork supply chain has a soil carbon loss of 0.49 tonnes carbon per 1000 kg pork fork weight and this is higher than in the conventional pork supply chain.

In general, the climate impact of pork found in this study compares well with previous E-LCA studies on pork. Most of these studies have the farm gate as a system boundary and use a functional unit of live weight or slaughter weight (75% of live weight). Our value at the farm gate was GWP 2.5 kg CO₂ eq per kg slaughter weight when agri-byproducts are included and 2.6 kg CO₂ eq per kg slaughter weight when agri-byproducts are not included – a finding that was in the same range as a recent study by RISE (2020). Compared with other European studies, GWP was comparable for conventional pork for a kg of slaughter weight at farm gate (Reckmann et al. 2013; Dalgaard et al. 2007 and Williams et al. 2006). Concerning GWP at the retail gate, our GWP value of 3.6 kg CO₂ eq per kg retail weight (59% of live weight) was in the range found in another recent study (Moberg et al. 2019). Our results for FEP, MEP, TAP100, FET, MET and TET were also in line with a recent LCA study from Spain by Noya et al. (2017), which calculated 18 environmental indicators for pork. In the con-

ventional pork supply chain having the slaughter gate as the system boundary in order to compare with Noya et al. (2017), indicates that 94–99% of the total impacts of FEP, MEP, TAP100, TET, FET, MET and HTP come from inputs, crop cultivation and pigs as shown in Fig. S2 to S8 in the supplementary. Our results for FDP are a departure from Noya et al. (2017). We had lower fossil fuel use for the farm and feed production stage (see Fig. S9) when compared with Noya et al. (2017) as a result of differences in distances travelled for transportation of farm inputs such as fertilizer, seeds and also pigs to the slaughterhouse. The distances in Spain are much longer than the distance we assumed for Sweden, so more fuel is required per kg pork. However, temperatures in Sweden are much lower, requiring more heating at the slaughterhouse per kg pork.

The sensitivity analysis results show that an increase in wheat and barley yields, together with the inclusion of agri-byproducts, reduced all environmental impact categories (Table S13). Replacement of soybean, rapeseed and faba beans in the total feed intake with agri-byproducts has a larger effect than increasing the yields for wheat and barley yields, especially on FEP, BDP, TET and SCL100. The large reductions in FEP were due to reduced leaching as a result of less soybean production and faba bean production, and in BDP the reductions in impacts were largely due to lower land use in the savanna biome for soybean production. The tropical savanna biome has higher species richness than temperate biomes (Cherubini et al. 2015). The reductions in carbon loss were associated with fewer losses resulting from less legume production. However, agri-byproducts are not free from impacts as such, and reductions in total impacts are not as high when the impacts of the agri-byproducts are taken into account. Thus, for example, when the GWP impact for agri-products was considered using economic allocation, GWP impact per kg pork was reduced by only 1%, whereas when the agri-byproducts were treated as free of environmental burden, the reduction was 7% (RISE 2020). The differences between our value of 4% when agri-byproducts are assumed to be free from environmental burden and 7% (RISE 2020) was that in our sensitivity analysis we replaced feed for slaughter pigs only and did not consider agri-byproduct use for the dry sows.

The use of an electric car decreased HTP by 5%, FEP by 3%, FDP by 2% and GWP by 1% in the conventional pork supply chain. The corresponding reduction figures for the organic pork supply chain were: HTP 6%, FEP 3%, FDP 2% and GWP 1%. Access to an outdoor environment increased MEP by 27%, TET by 17%, FEP by 3%, GWP by 1%, HTP by 2% and TAP100 by 9% in the conventional pork supply chain. This means that the provision of outdoor access increases negative environmental impacts, especially for MEP, as a result of N leaching caused by spatial and temporal distribution of N following pig movements in the outdoor area. The sensitiv-

Table 6

Value Added over Life Cycle Costs plus labor costs ratio (expressed in Swedish krona) for 1000 kg pork fork weight and 1000 ha of farmland in the pork supply chains.

Indicator	Impacts per 1000 kg pork		Impacts per 1000 ha farmland	
	Conventional	Organic	Conventional	Organic
VA/(LCC + labor costs) farm	1.1	0.83	1.1	0.83
VA/(LCC + labor costs) slaughterhouse	5.1	4.9	5.0	4.9
VA/(LCC + labor costs) wholesaler and retailer	13	27	13	26

VA- value added

LCC – Life Cycle Costing

ity analysis indicates that GWP emissions are 4% lower when all the ammonium nitrate used is produced using the N₂O reduction technology that reduces nitrous oxide emissions by 90%.

4.2. Life Cycle Costing

Our results showed that the VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for pig farmers in the conventional pork supply chain was higher than that for farmers in the organic pork supply chain. Farm production in the conventional pork supply chain generates more value than the organic equivalent for every SEK invested in LCC + labor costs per 1000 kg pork fork weight and 1000 ha of farmland used, as shown in Table 6. The VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for the pig farm in the organic pork supply chain was less than 1, suggesting that a farmer creates less value compared to the amount invested for LCC and has less money remaining to meet expenses such as interest, depreciation and also make a profit in the end. However, here we considered neither the value of ecosystem services provided by the farm nor the fact that farmers often work without remunerating themselves. The latter however cannot be considered economically sustainable. When the results were expressed per 1000 ha farmland used instead of per 1000 kg pork fork weight, the conventional pork supply chain still performed better than its organic counterpart at the farm, reflecting greater economic activity (i.e. higher production) per hectare. There was no difference between VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for the 1000 kg pork fork weight and 1000 ha farmland used, because the increases in value added and costs were proportional. The conventional pork supply chain has the higher VA/(LCC + labor cost) for the farmers, and the organic pork supply chain has the higher VA/(LCC + labor cost) for other supply chain actors, indicating that the increased willingness to pay for organic meat among consumers does not reach the farmer. However, it should be noted that for the wholesaler and retailer, VA/(LCC + labor costs) was larger than it was for other chain actors, partly as a consequence of vertical integration (i.e. one and the same actor performing wholesaling and retailing).

Measured per 1000 kg pork fork weight, the LCC + labor costs at the farm were 1.5 times more in the organic pork supply chain owing to higher labor cost and costs related to lower efficiency (e.g. more feed required per kg pork and lower crop yields in the organic supply chain: see Table S8 in the supplementary). Moreover, value-added (VA) at the farm was almost twice as high in the organic pork supply chain than it was in the conventional pork supply chain as a result of the higher price for organic pork (see Table S14 in the supplementary). Measured per 1000 ha of farmland, the organic pork supply chain had 19% higher costs at the farm than the conventional pork supply chain (see Table S8 in the supplementary). Value-added was also 8% higher at the conventional farm (see Table S14 in the supplementary) and there was a large difference between the conventional and the organic pork supply chain in labor costs at the farm (Fig. S10).

The organic pork supply chain had higher VA/(LCC + labor costs) for the slaughterhouse, and for the wholesaler and retailer, than the conventional pork supply chain. This can be explained

by the substantially higher selling prices both at the slaughterhouse (17 SEK/kg slaughter weight for conventional and 35 SEK/kg slaughter weight for organic) and at wholesaler and retailer (respectively, 42 SEK/kg retail weight and 67 SEK/kg retail weight) (Lars Jonasson personal communication 2020) when these are compared with LCC which are the same for both supply chains (see Table S8 in the supplementary). There was also a huge increase in value at the end of the supply chain because low costs were associated with vertical integration, post farm actors had higher margins and also because we did not consider processed meats but only fresh raw meat. The results emphasize that farmers do not generate value as other chain actors do. The large difference in VA/(LCC + labor cost) ratio between the wholesaler and retailer and the farmer is an example of the unequal distribution of profits across food chain actors in the EU reported by Kelly (2019), an inequality we found to be especially pronounced in the organic pork supply chain.

The VA/(LCC + labor costs) farm results for this study show that conventional pig production created more value than the life cycle and labor costs when compared to organic pig production, indicating a higher opportunity of profitability than in organic pig production. However, profits in organic production vary: some farmers report higher profits while others have indicated lower profits when compared to conventional production (Larsson 2014). Confidentiality issues mean that we have no empirical studies to the best of our knowledge indicating gross profit margins or net profits for pig production in Europe generally.

Change in pork producer price has the greatest effect on the VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio, followed by soy price change (Table S15). Change in wheat and barley yields have a notable effect in comparison with other crops produced at the farm because they are the main feed ingredients. The conventional pork supply chain still performs better than the organic pork supply chain at the farm when soybean price and pork producer price are altered in the sensitivity analyses. Access to an outdoor environment decreased the VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for the conventional farm by 11%. This means that providing pigs access to outdoor environment has a negative economic effect, given that it is not used in marketing conventional pork, which could raise the consumer price of the pork. A 5% increase in salary decreased the VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for the farm by 2% in both pork supply chains. Removing labor costs (as they vary from farm to farm) and thus having the VA/LCC ratio, results in both supply chains creating more value than the amount invested for LCC. The conventional pork supply chain has VA/LCC equal to 1.7 and organic pork supply chain has VA/LCC equal to 1.4 at the farm, but these are still below the other value chain actors.

4.3. Social Life Cycle Assessment

The social assessment per 1000 kg of pork fork weight produced showed that the organic pork supply chain performs better (i.e. has a smaller SRT) than the conventional pork supply chain for value chain actors, society, consumers and pigs (see Table 7). In

Table 7

The Social Risk Time for 1000 kg pork fork weight and 1000 ha of farmland in the pork supply chains (higher of the two marked in bold).

Stakeholder	Units	Impacts per 1000 kg pork		Impacts per 1000 ha farmland	
		Conventional	Organic	Conventional	Organic
Workers	Medium risk hours	52 000	56 000	29 000 000	14 000 000
Local community	Medium risk hours	74 000	93 000	43 000 000	24 000 000
Value chain actors	Medium risk hours	48 000	31 000	27 000 000	8 600 000
Society	Medium risk hours	69 000	46 000	39 000 000	12 000 000
Consumer	Risk people days	44 000	19 000	25 000 000	4 900 000
Pigs	Risk pig life days	280 000	130 000	160 000 000	32 000 000

contrast, the conventional pork supply chain had smaller SRT for *workers* and the *local community*. This is explained by higher values of the activity variables in the organic pork supply chain (where more working hours are needed to produce 1000 kg of pork fork weight than are needed for the conventional pork supply chain) and the larger SRs in the organic pork supply chain. An increase in working hours has a positive impact on employment, which is favorable from a societal point of view, but when the work is associated with higher social risks, as captured by the SRs, this gives a large SRT, and this is unfavorable. The social assessment per 1000 ha of farmland confirmed that the organic pork supply chain performs better for all stakeholders. This outcome was due to there being less economic activity per hectare, giving lower output and hence lower activity variables.

The higher SRT for *workers* for the organic pork supply chains resulted from differences in values relating to the gender wage gap, trade unionism and risk of violation of employment laws and regulations, as shown in Table S16 in the supplementary. Most of the impacts in the organic pork supply chain emanate from soybean production (Fig. S11). Soybean is imported from China in the organic pork supply chain, whereas in the conventional pork supply chain it is sourced in Brazil. If certification schemes such as the Roundtable on Responsible Soy (RTRS) for conventional soybean and KRAV for organic soybean are not working properly, the risks become higher. Assuming the schemes are not working properly, SRT increases by 2% for *workers* in Brazil and 16% for *workers* in China. These results were expected given China's lower human freedom rankings than Brazil's (Vásquez and Porčnik 2019).

The differences in SRT for the *local community* were caused by difference in fossil fuel consumption, international migrant stock and non-fatal accidents in electricity generation and distribution. The use of renewable energy from solar sources at the pig farm in the organic pork supply chain resulted in higher social impacts for *workers* and the *local community* because there are more accidents in renewable energy production (Fig. S11). This has also been reported by Stamford and Azapagic (2012) in a life cycle sustainability assessment of electricity in the United Kingdom. The organic pork supply chain used more diesel, especially for wheat and barley production due to mechanical weed control, since pesticides were not used. The yields were lower here, and more feed per kg pork was required. More light fuel oil for drying crops was also required, because of more feed as well.

The differences in SRT for *value chain actors* were caused by differences in values for corruption in Brazil and China. These results accord with Brazil's lower transparency rankings than China's (Transparency International 2020). For *society*, the differences in SRT were caused by differences in literacy and health expenditure between Brazil and China. These are indicators which, on a general level, capture the social situation in different countries. The results here were expected, because Brazil has a lower literacy rate than China (World Bank 2020b), and also because in Brazil the government contribution to health expenditure is lower, as a percentage

of health spending per capita, than in China (World Health Organization 2020).

For some of the key inputs in the pork supply chain, Sweden was not fully represented in all sectors in Soca, and here, therefore, we used alternative countries with production conditions similar to those in Sweden. For example, for wheat production we used German social risk indicators. Obviously, this method relies on national similarities and can lead to the underestimation or overestimation of social impacts, so our results must be read with caution.

SRT depends on the weight of the indicators. In Zira et al. (2020) an expert panel was used in setting the weightings of the indicators. Here, no explicit weighting was undertaken, and all indicators were weighted equally. However, the way the scales are set up can create an indirect weighting. Thus, consider the indicator *percentage of pigs with bitten tails* (Table S12). This indicator has six levels of risk on the reference scale: no risk (0), very low risk (0.01), low risk (0.1), medium risk (1), high risk (10) and very high risk (100). Five percent of the pigs have bitten tails and this was assigned a low risk level, the activity variable for the indicator will hence be multiplied by 0.1, meaning a low contribution to SRT. Now compare an indicator like *percentage of tail-docked pigs* with just two levels, where no docking is set at no risk (0) and docking is set at very high risk (100). Here, if 5% of the pigs are tail-docked, the activity variable is multiplied by 100. It can be seen that the indicator *percentage of tail-docked pigs* has more weight because it has fewer performance reference points but the same starting point and endpoint as a normal reference scale with six reference points. The reference scales are context-specific and expert opinion was used to define them so that a weighting in between indicators was also performed. Defining different endpoints or risk levels for the worse option can be seen as an alternative to the differential weighting of different indicators employed by Zira et al. (2020) in a previous S-LCA on pork.

In Zira et al. (2020) a linear scale (with risk values between 0 and 1) was used. This resulted in the activity variable T (i.e. the time of exposure) having a large effect on SRT in comparison with social risk. Hence prolonged exposure at low social risk could result in considerably higher SRT than a high but brief social risk. As this may, in some cases, disfavor systems which require more time but have low social risk, Zira et al. (2020) used an index, the Social Hotspot Index, in which each system was compared with its respective worst-case scenario (when SR was at its maximum value) thereby cancelling the effect of T. In the present study, however, there was less need to do this, because an exponential reference scale (with risk values between 0-100) was used for SR, decreasing the importance of T at high social risk values.

As for *pigs* and *consumers*, the results we report here are comparable with those presented in our previous study (Zira et al. 2020). In other words, the organic pork supply chain has lower social risk for pigs and consumers than the conventional pork supply chain, because organic pigs have outside access and

more opportunities to express natural behavior, and because organic pork meat is valued more highly by consumers. The results are less comparable for *workers*, *local community* and *society*, because in our previous study we dwelt on *direct* social sustainability issues raised against pork production that were collected for all the stakeholders whereas in this study we focus on a general social inventory of indicators for pork supply chains presented in Soca (Table S1). The general social inventory of indicators in Soca omits indicators of work-related ill health specifically associated with pork production, such as musculoskeletal disorders and direct assessment of pesticide toxicity for soybean production. Pesticide toxicity is, however, partly taken into account in 'presence of safety measures'. They also do not include gender equality as measured by the number of males/females employed, the status of the production activity in society (e.g. pig farming may be considered a low status employment in Sweden), age discrimination, and access to products (e.g. through on-farm stores). All of these were considered in our previous study (Zira et al. 2020). Another reason for the discrepancy for *local community* and *society* is that the same activity variable, *work hours*, is used for all these stakeholders. In contrast, in our previous study (Zira et al. 2020), we used different activity variables for different stakeholders. We recognize that the change of the activity variable from *hectare days* in Zira et al. (2020) to *work hours* in the present study led to a decrease in SRT in the organic pork supply chain. In other words, there was a change from a larger activity variable based on the area of land used multiplied by *work hours* to a smaller activity variable based on *work hours* alone, and this resulted in the organic pork supply chain coming out, in respect of its impacts on society, than the conventional pork supply chain, when the two were compared per 1000 kg of pork fork weight, in a way that was not observed in Zira et al. (2020). It is arguably better to use *hectare days* because the social risk impact for *society* from crop production is influenced more by the amount of land used and the time between planting and harvesting for a crop than it is by *work hours*. This suggests that the best practice in assessing social risk impacts in S-LCA involving crop production might be to use *hectare days* for *society* as well as *local community* and *work hours* for *workers* and *farmers* as the activity variables. But more research is needed in this area.

The sensitivity analysis (Table S17) suggests that a change in the soybean source to a high-income country has a largely favorable effect on the social risk on *workers* and the *local community* in the organic pork supply chain but no effect in the conventional pork supply chain. This result indicates the difference in the social conditions of labor and human rights between China and Switzerland. It also illustrates the change in social risk that might occur if the soybean source is changed. We selected Switzerland because it produces organic and conventional soybean and is present in Soca. However, such a country may not be viable in reality, as low quantities of soybeans are produced in Switzerland (and indeed in Europe generally). There was no notable difference between Brazil and Switzerland for social impacts because trade unionism in Brazil is similar to that in Switzerland, according to the information in Soca. Brazil has 18 000 unions, and these can negotiate for better working conditions (Menezes-Filho et al. 2008). However, in China there is a single trade union system, the All-China Federation of Trade Unions (ACFTU), and its genuine willingness, or ability, to represent workers' interests has been contested, especially since its office holders are not elected themselves (Lambert and Webster 2017). There was also no notable difference between Brazil and Switzerland because Soca misses the indicators on work-related sickness, such as pesticide effects on deoxyribonucleic acid, which were captured in Zira et al. (2020). Change in the soybean source alters the result pattern: with this change, the organic pork supply chain performs better than the conventional pork supply chain for all stakeholders. The improvement of social conditions in China,

or replacement of soybean with other protein sources produced in Europe, could reduce social risk impacts in the organic pork supply chain.

Increased access to the outdoor environment resulted in an 8% increase in impacts each for *workers* and *local community*, a 5% increase for *society*, and a 16% decrease in the impacts for *pigs*. Although providing access to the outdoor environment has some favorable effects for the pigs, it negatively affects other stakeholders since it raises work hours. The +20% yield change in wheat and barley (one at a time), each reduced impacts for all stakeholders by 2% and the -20% yield change in wheat and barley, each increased impacts for all stakeholders by 3% for the conventional pork supply chain. For the organic pork supply chain, the $\pm 20\%$ yield change in barley, changed impacts for all stakeholders by $\pm 1\%$.

4.4. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

Relative Sustainability Point (RSP) scores range from 0 to 1, and the conventional pork supply chain is the benchmark (at 0.5) (Fig. 2). Low RSP (< 0.5) therefore means that the organic pork supply chain is more sustainable than the conventional pork supply chain. The organic pork supply chain performs worse than its conventional counterpart in 9 out of 20 product-based indicators when these are compared for the production of 1000 kg pork fork weight, mostly as a result of environmental indicators (Fig. 2). The organic pork supply chain outperforms the conventional for 18 of the 20 indicators when the results are expressed per unit area (Fig 2). This means that if decision makers emphasize the negative impacts pork supply chains have on the ecosystem per unit area of land, the organic system is preferable. However, for indicators such as eutrophication and acidification, the lower yields of the organic pork supply chain result in higher impacts on a product basis.

Access to outdoor environment improves social performance for pigs in the conventional pork supply chain. However, it leads to higher environmental impacts such as GWP and MEP per kg of pork, and to an increased risk of diseases such as toxoplasmosis (Kijlstra et al. 2004), higher social risk for workers, and greater feed costs (because more feed is required per kg pork) (Stern et al. 2003). This is in accordance with (Rossi and Garner (2014), Appleby (2005) and Hendrickson and James (2005), all of whom argue that animal welfare generates environmental costs and more expensive meat for society. This points up the difficulties involved in making improvements in all three sustainability pillars. The complexities here are due to unavoidable trade-offs between social and environmental sustainability and social and economic sustainability.

Improving soybean sustainability by increasing the cultivation of soybean in Southern Europe (Chancellor 2018) may reduce the social risk for the stakeholder category *workers* in the pork supply chain, as shown in the sensitivity analysis for soybean origin in the organic pork supply chain. This may not affect environmental impacts such as GWP and FDP, but it will lead to a reduction of the VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio for pig farmers, as indicated in the sensitivity analysis for increased soybean price. This may also lead to loss of income opportunities for soybean producers in Brazil and China, an effect that our analysis of social impacts failed to capture. The use of robots in the pork supply chain, at the slaughterhouse (Valente et al. 2020) and possibly at the farms in Brazil or China, could reduce the social risk for labor-intensive activities, reduce labor costs and provide more jobs for educated and skilled labor, but it could also reduce employment for the less skilled (Marinoudi et al. 2019). This remains difficult to capture with attributional S-LCA and may be best captured by consequential S-LCA (Zamagni et al. 2011).

Incorporating agri-byproducts in the pigs' diets and increasing yields (without increased use of fertilizers) can improve the en-

Fig. 2. Life cycle sustainability assessment in Relative Sustainability Points (RSP) for the organic pork supply chain for 1000 kg pork fork weight and 1000 ha of farmland with the conventional pork supply chain as the reference (RSP=0.5) with VA/LCC being the Value Added over Life Cycle Cost + Labor Costs.

environmental impacts per kg pork, such as GWP, and the economic impact through a higher VA/(LCC + labor costs) ratio and lower social risk for workers, especially for soybean. Agri-byproducts exhibit a synergy between social, environmental and economic impacts. However, competition for byproducts for other uses, the cultural acceptability of byproduct use, and the fact that the availability of byproducts is driven by the main product, all limit the potential of using byproducts (van Zanten et al. 2018; Rööß et al. 2016). Having more byproducts in pig diets going forward may therefore be difficult. Adjusting the pig population so that it is commensurate with ecological limits and the availability of byproducts could be a solution here (van Zanten et al. 2018). However, there will always be an opportunity cost, because byproducts are used or can be used for other purposes as well.

Assuming equal importance of economic, environmental, and social life-cycle indicators (i.e., equal weights), the most sustainable supply chain, when comparing different supply chains, is the one with lower RSP for most indicators. From an indicator expressed per unit area perspective, the organic pork supply chain is more sustainable (RSP organic < RSP conventional for 18 of 20 indicators). The increased competition for agricultural land and the increased demand for animal products are reasons for a product-based perspective, and then the assessment result is less clear (RSP organic < RSP conventional for 11 of 20 indicators). Another way to compare different pork supply chains is to define the most sustainable one as the one with most indicators with lower RSP for both indicators expressed per unit area and unit product. In this LCSA, the organic pork supply chain has lower RSP for 11 indicators expressed both per unit area and unit product, and the conventional pork supply chain has lower RSP for 1 indicator expressed both per unit area and unit product.

This study's results provide a basis for future planning of a new business model for reducing negative impacts of pork production without focusing on food provisioning alone. The pork supply chain, as envisaged in the new business model, should improve social welfare for stakeholders, including pigs, maintain or improve economic benefits and mitigate environmental impacts. Elements of the new model are likely to include allowing pigs access to distraction material or an outdoor environment, optimizing the use of by-products in pig diets, obtaining higher yields in organic pro-

duction, and ensuring there is a viable producer price for slaughter pigs. Kelly (2019) reports challenges in food supply chains in the EU caused by the unfair distribution of profits in the supply chain. Our results could help farmer organizations in the pork supply chain to lobby for better conditions, and returns, for farmers in future.

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment has the advantage of integrating environmental, economic and social indicators, and thereby showing the trade-offs between these three pillars of sustainability. However, the identification of suitable indicators is a challenging task, and indicator selection and scaling heavily influence results of the assessment. In addition, social and economic data are not available at the same level of detail as environmental data. A degree of arbitrariness remains in the design of the algorithm to calculate impacts, especially where social impacts are concerned. Other challenges revolve around the communication of results to decision-makers and the question whether the weighting and aggregation of the indicators enhances the overall interpretation. These should be further researched.

5. Conclusions

Assessed with the 20 indicators used in this LCSA, the organic pork supply chain is clearly more sustainable than its conventional counterpart when the assessment is based on indicators expressed per unit area (agricultural land). On the other hand, the greater quantity of feed required to produce a kg of pork and the lower yields in the organic pork supply chain cause the organic pork supply chain to perform less well for indicators expressed per unit product. Inevitably, the picture is complex. The organic pork supply chain performs better than the conventional one in terms of human toxicity and ecotoxicity, biodiversity loss, better pig welfare, lower social risk for consumers, society and value chain actors, and in delivering more value added at the slaughterhouse, and wholesaler and retailer, than the conventional pork supply chain. However, it performs less well than the conventional pork supply chain on a per kg pork basis for eutrophication, acidification, fossil resources use, and in the value added when a comparison is made with life cycle costs and labor costs at the farm, and the social risks for workers and local community. The organic pork supply

chain promotes social well-being for pigs, but it consumes more resources, especially land, and has a higher leakage of nitrogen as a result of the greater amount of feed required to produce a kg of pork together with lower crop yields. The conventional pork supply chain is more resource-efficient, in that more pork is produced per unit area and in terms of the financial resources used, but pesticide use results in higher human toxicity and ecotoxicity.

The redesign of both pork supply chains is required to make them more sustainable, and this could include consideration of the following three points. Firstly, the need for an increase in wheat and barley yields (through improvements in managements and with limited additional inputs) because higher yields for these feed crops reduce environmental, social and economic impacts in both pork supply chains. Secondly, the need for improved animal welfare in the conventional pork supply chain in order for welfare to approach the organic pork supply chain, where pigs have indicated better welfare due to outdoor access, access to distraction material and the possibility to express natural behavior. Lastly, the farmers need to receive a fair slaughter price that results in at least Value Added over Life Cycle Costs plus labor costs ratio ($VA/(LCC + \text{labor costs})$) equal to one, which is currently not the case for the studied organic pork supply chain. Trade-offs between environmental, economic and social sustainability should be considered in the redesigning of the pork supply chains.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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